

Calculation of Individual Sustainable Absorption for IMACS

1. Abstract

This article describes a universally standardized method to calculate the amounts of environmental and human resources an individual can use sustainably. The sustainable resource amount calculated for each resource type used, must be deducted from the individual's resources consumed to calculate the net resource use of the individual's labor. Besides resources used, the Individual Sustainable Absorption (ISA) also depends on the amount of conservation that is applied to render the use of the resource sustainable. The same applies to restoration applied to offset current and historic damage done. The ISA calculation is the essential element of the Individual Supply Chain Step (ISCS) calculation which is in turn part of the Impact Measurement and Conservation System (IMACS). Sustainably available resource use and protection applied as well as the required amounts of restoration applied to historic damage can be calculated and must be deducted as ISA and thus removed from the supply chain. The ISA calculation allows the calculation of the excess (non-sustainable) resource use as well as the net amounts of current damage done and historic damage assigned to individuals. The ISA is calculated based on the EH-impacts of the consumption for each individual and their comparison to the EH-impacts of the consumption for a 100% sustainable (= reference) individual. The combination of the ISCS inputs and the calculated ISA, allows calculation of the environ-humane (EH) impacts of the labor output of the individual, which in turn allows the calculation of the (EH) impacts of products and services. Implementation of IMACS allows a potentially fast return to pre-industrial environmental conditions (e.g. reversal of global warming and restoration of global biodiversity and elimination of water scarcity) and allows large improvements in human conditions.

2. Introduction

Various methods exist to estimate and add a few types of environmental impacts over a defined period and to assign these to an individual (1, 2, 3, 4, 5). While these methods can be applied on different population scales, they are based on average consumptions. No methods exist where individual consumption is calculated separately for every individual from EH-impacts for each product and service by type, brand and location of sale. In addition, no methods exist where such impact amounts can be calculated for a large number of environmental and humane conditions impacts and can be corrected for the amounts the individual can sustainably use for each impact variable. No system exists allowing the calculation of damaging environ-human (EH) impacts for all products, services for individuals. No system exists allowing the application of conservation to neutralize damaging EH-impacts, potentially rendering products and services (and individuals) free of EH-impacts.

The Impact Measurement And Conservation System (IMACS) was developed to measure the and human condition impacts of products, services and individuals (6, 7). The Individual Supply Chain Step (ISCS) is used as an integral part of IMACS calculations. The ISCS allows calculation of environ-human (EH) impacts of the individual labor product ("labor"). To do so the calculation of the Individual Sustainable Absorption (ISA) of the individual is needed. An earlier paper describing the IMAC system and ISCSs did not include the calculation of the Individual Sustainable Absorption (ISA) under non-reference conditions.

3. Calculation of Individual Sustainable Absorption (ISA)

3.1. ISA Function and Names

Certain amounts of resource use, damage and conservation applied are deducted as Individual Sustainable absorption (ISA) in an ISA output block attached to each ISCS. The function of Individual Sustainable Absorption (ISA) is to remove EH impacts from the supply chain that should not end up as EH impacts in the labor output. For

example; the amount of Cultivated Area (CA) that is used by and sustainably available to an individual should not end up in their labor output, but should be removed from the supply chain. If not done so, the CA amount in the labor output would increase the CA use of products made with each production cycle and thus “accumulate” in the supply chain. The name “Individual Sustainable Absorption” (ISA) is used as a general name. Different names are used for each variable type:

- ISLA: Individual Sustainable Labor Absorption (for labor hours)
- ISRA: Individual Sustainable Resource-use Absorption for allowance variables
- ICDA: Individual Current Damage Absorption for current damage variables
- IHDA: Individual Historic Damage Absorption for historic damage variables

The ISA is calculated differently for each of the different types of variables (labor, allowance, current damage and historic damage). In order to reach sustainable conditions, all required conservation must be applied at time of resource use and/or damage done. Any conservation deficit creates additional damage due to 2nd and higher order effects. This higher order damage is calculated and recorded as additional current damage assigned to the individual and will be discussed in later publications. Any individual environmental (E) resource use above allowances and any current and historic EH damage not matched by EH restoration ends up in the labor output.

3.2. Individual Sustainable Labor Hour Absorption (ISLA)

The hours worked represent a human impact variable. To maintain humane conditions, labor hours worked per time should not be excessive; labor hours worked thus represent an allowance variable. To catch excessive labor hour conditions, the hours worked must be recorded on a daily basis. Labor hours worked per unit time can best be called “*labor hour intensity*”. However, all ISCS and associated calculations use a combination of inputs of “*hours worked*” expressed in hours and the period over which these hours are counted. Using these inputs the “*labor hour intensity*” expressed in h/w, can be calculated as a derived variable. The *labor hours* worked is a variable representing H-impact flowing in and out of ISCS and we need to calculate the ISLA in order to correctly close the labor hour impact balance over the ISCS. All environmental impacts are initially expressed as original variable with units, but can be normalized (6, 7) by dividing by their corresponding reference values (=100% sustainable conditions) or representative values (the typical value used to represent the average damage). Original variable symbols are written in capitals, with normalized variable symbols are written in *italic* small print. To make excessive labor visible to the end-use consumer buying products and services, excessive labor hours worked (slave, child and sweatshop labor) need to show up in the labor output and never more than the reference labor hours ($l = 1$) should be deducted as ISLA. If the individual works part time (or is retired) no more than the actual hours worked should be deducted as ISLA in order to allow forwarding of excessive labor hours from products consumed to the labor output. To prevent reducing the labor hour component in the labor output, never more labor hours can be deducted as ISA than were present in the individual’s consumption. The calculation of labor hours to be deducted as ISLA (l_{ISLA}) is independent of the variable type u_m . The ISLA value is the minimum of the reference individual labor hours, the individual labor hours worked and the amount of labor hours represented by the products and services consumed.

$$l_{ISLA} = \text{MIN}(1, l_{worked}, l_{consumed}) \quad (1)$$

where l_{ISLA}	= normalized individual sustainable labor hour absorption	[h/y]
where l_{worked}	= normalized individual labor hours worked by the individual represented by the ISCS	[h/y]
where $l_{consumed}$	= labor hours corresponding with products and services consumed by the individual	[h/y]

The allowance variable for individual hour intensity is one of the many human condition variables of which most will be added once data on such variables are available. Once enough EH impact data are available for the goods and services consumed by the individual, the upper half of the distribution of labor hours intensity will be calculated from which better measures of excessive working conditions can be derived (see Methods). Salary paid flows in resource direction. The full amount of salary paid flows out with the employee consumption of goods and services. These consumptions include all types of spending and include taxes (payments for government services).

3.3. Individual Sustainable Resource Use Absorption (ISRA)

Under IMACS, the use of natural resources by humans is considered to be environmental damage, unless a sufficient amount of the same resource is protected such that no biodiversity losses would result now or in the future as a result of the resource use. For each individual, a certain amount of natural resource use (“*the allowance*”) is sustainably available for each “allowance” variable, but only when the required amounts of conservation are applied. Any use of natural resources within an allowance but without the required conservation applied is no longer sustainably available and thus considered environmental damage and unsustainable. Any use of natural resources in excess of the allowance is unsustainable and would result in less than 100% resource use sustainability for the particular natural resource use variable. Even so, in case of excess resource use for allowance variables, conservation corresponding to the total resource use is still required in order to reach 100% conservation sustainability. In case the resource use allowance is exactly used, while the required conservation is applied, both the resource use and conservation are removed from the supply chain as Individual Sustainable Resource use Absorption (ISRA). Any reduced use of the resource or any shortfall in conservation applied, results in a reduction of the (ISRA) for the variables considered.

Figure 1: ISCS reflecting reference conditions expressed as original variables for cultivated area use (an allowance variable) using example values over a one-week period. Except for financial compensations paid, all EH-impacts flow from left (resources) to right (end-users) through the figure. L = labor hours worked (h), U = resources used (Ha.w), P = conservation applied (Ha.w) and C = salary paid (\$). To convert to EH impact rates, all values need to be divided by the accounting period: L/w = labor intensity (h/w), U/w = resource use rate (Ha), P/w = conservation rate (Ha) and C/w = salary rate (\$/w). EH impacts of labor output are equal to the sum of all EH impact inputs minus the PSA EH impacts. Per definition, under reference conditions, the resource use is equal to the allowance, conservation applied is equal to requirements, while resource use and conservation applied leave the supply chain as PSA rendering the labor output free of E-impacts.

For example; for cultivated area (CA) used, a certain amount of wildlife area (WA) needs to be protected in the same ecoregion. This ratio is expressed as $R_{Bio} = P_{WA,Ref} / U_{CA,Ref}$, where $U_{CA,Ref}$ is the individual allowance and $P_{WA,Ref}$ is the wildlife area required to be protected to make the cultivated area $U_{CA,Ref}$ sustainably available (6). The ratio R_{Bio} is also applied to the actual CA used. In that case $R_{Bio} = P_{WA,Req} / U_{CA}$, where U_{CA} represents the CA used and $P_{WA,Req}$ the WA required to be protected. For $R_{Bio} = 1.5$ and $U_{CA} = 2$ Ha the required conservation value for P is $P_{WA,Req} = 1.5 * U_{CA} = 3$ Ha. For allowance variables, the normalized reference individual is represented by $[l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 1, 1] | [1]$. This is independent of the ratio R_{Bio} . For a CA allowance of 0.8 Ha ($U_{CA,Ref} = 0.8$ Ha) and a ratio $R_{Bio} = 1.5$, an individual using 0.8 Ha of CA while protecting ($P_{CA,Ref} = U_{CA,Ref} * R_{Bio} = 0.8 * 1.5 = 1.2$ Ha) of WA, u and p are calculated as:

$$u = U_{CA} / U_{CA,Ref} = 0.8 \text{ Ha} / 0.8 \text{ Ha} = 1.0$$

$$p = P_{CA} / P_{CA,Ref} = 1.2 \text{ Ha} / 1.2 \text{ Ha} = 1.0$$

If instead the individual uses twice as much CA ($U_{CA} = 1.6$ Ha), but also protects twice as much WA ($P_{CA} = 2.4$ Ha), then we calculate:

$$u = U_{CA} / U_{CA,Ref} = 1.6 \text{ Ha} / 0.8 \text{ Ha} = 2.0$$

$$p = P_{CA} / P_{CA,Ref} = 2.4 \text{ Ha} / 1.2 \text{ Ha} = 2.0$$

Reference conditions cases for CA use expressed as original and normalized variables are shown in figures 1 and 2. In case the ratio $R_{Bio} = 1.0$, the required amounts of wildlife area to be conserved would be smaller, but would lead to the same values for u and p . Therefore, under reference conditions $p = u = 1$, while under non-reference

conditions where the required amount of conservation is applied, $p = u \neq 1$. When $p \neq u$, then either not enough or too much conservation is applied. In all cases, the values for u and p are independent of the value for the ratio R_{Bio} .

Starting with the values for the original (non-normalized) variables U_{CA} and P_{WA} , the cultivated area used for goods and services consumed and wildlife area protected can be expressed over a defined period and on a portfolio basis. Using the reference values $U_{CA,Ref}$ and $P_{WA,Ref}$ for the original allowance variables, the normalized variable values u_{CA} and p_{WA} can be calculated. In case $u_{CA} = 1 = u_{CA,Ref}$, the required wildlife area to be protected is $p_{WA,Ref} = 1$. If the cultivated area allowance is fully used ($u_{CA} = 1$), but the actual wildlife area protected corresponds to $p_{WA} = 0.5$, only half of u_{CA} consumed was sustainably available and only this half can be absorbed as ISRA. In contrast to restoration applied for damage variables (e.g. C-sequestration) excess resource use cannot be undone by restoration, but still requires conservation. For allowance variables, all EH impact amounts used in excess of the sustainably available amounts ends up in the labor product. The same applies to excess conservation applied.

Figure 2: ISCS corresponding to normalized reference conditions for allowance and historic damage variables, reflecting the example values of figure 1. l = labor hours worked, u_m = resources used, p_n = conservation applied and c = salary paid. All values are unit-less.

For the unspecified normalized allowance variable u_m and the corresponding normalized conservation variable p_n the resource use amounts u_m and conservation p_n that needs to be absorbed as ISRA are:

- never more than is sustainably available: $u_{m,ISRA} \leq u_{m,SA} = \text{MIN}(u_{m,Ref}, p_n)$
- never more than was consumed: $u_{m,ISRA} \leq u_m$

For allowance variables the amount of conservation that can be absorbed as ISRA is:

- Never more than applied for reference consumer: $p_{n,ISRA} \leq p_{n,Ref} = 1$
- Never more than is required: $p_{n,ISRA} \leq p_{n,Req} = u_{m,Cons}$
- Never more than was applied: $p_{n,ISRA} \leq p_{n,Cons}$

where $u_{m,ISRA}$ = individual resource use absorption for allowance variable u_m [IU]

where $u_{m,Cons}$ = individual resource use consumption for allowance variable u_m [IU]

where $u_{m,SA}$ = individual sustainably available amount of resource use for allowance variable u_m [IU]

where $u_{m,Ref}$ = individual reference value (allowance) for allowance variable u_m [IU]

where $p_{n,ISRA}$ = individual sustainable absorption for conservation variable p_n , associated with variable u_m [IU]

where $p_{n,Cons}$ = conservation applied for conservation variable p_n , associated with allowance variable u_m [IU]

where $p_{n,Ref}$ = reference amount of conservation for variable p_n , associated with allowance variable u_m [IU]

where $p_{n,Req}$ = required conservation for conservation variable p_n , associated with allowance variable u_m [IU]

Note: Units "IU" stands for "impact units" and depend on the resource use variable used.

Combining the above, for normalized allowance variable u_m and the corresponding conservation variable p_n , the ISRA values are calculated as:

$$u_{m,ISRA} = \text{MIN}(u_{m,Ref}, u_{m,Cons}, p_{n,Cons}) = \text{MIN}(1, u_{m,Cons}, p_{n,Cons}) \quad (2)$$

$$p_{n,ISRA} = \text{MIN}(p_{n,Ref}, p_{n,Req}, p_{n,Cons}) = \text{MIN}(1, u_{m,Cons}, p_{n,Cons}) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Indicating that this applies to allowance variables: } p_{n,ISRA} = u_{m,ISRA} = \text{MIN}(1, u_{m,All,Cons}, p_{n,All,Cons}) \quad (4)$$

3.4. Individual Current Damage Absorption (ICDA)

For current damage variables, no allowances exist. Under reference conditions both the current damage done and the conservation required are zero. Under non-sustainable current damage conditions, EH damage is done and the required amount of conservation applied is equal to the current damage done. If less than the required restoration is applied, the balance of the current damage done and restored needs to be carried forward by the labor output and less damage can be deducted as ICDA. The same applies to excess restoration applied. This means that only matching amounts for u_m and p_n can be adsorbed as ICDA. The resulting ICDA is:

$$u_{m,ICDA} = p_{n,ICDA} = \text{MIN}(u_{m,CD,Cons}, p_{n,CD,Cons}) \quad (5)$$

where $u_{m,ICDA}$ = individual sustainable current damage absorption for current damage variable u_m [IU]

where $p_{n,ICDA}$ = individual sustainable current damage absorption for conservation variable p_n , associated with current damage variable u_m [IU]

where $u_{m,CD,Cons}$ = individual current damage for allowance variable u_m [IU]

where $p_{n,CD,Cons}$ = conservation applied for variable p_n , associated with current damage variable u_m [IU]

Any amount of current damage in excess of conservation applied and any amounts of conservation applied in excess of current damage done, ends up in the labor output of the ISCS. To reach and maintain 100% conservation sustainability, all current damage must be fully and immediately restored by applying the required amount of conservation for the appropriate conservation variables. Carbon (C) emissions are one form of such damages and C-emissions need to be reduced to zero ASAP. This prevents the need to remove these C-emissions by C-sequestration. In addition, C-sequestration capacity used to offset current C-emissions, reduces the remaining capacity to sequester historic C-emissions and increases the restoration period needed to reach year 1750 conditions.

3.5. Individual Historic Damage Absorption (IHDA)

For each historic environmental damage variable, a certain amount of restoration to original environmental conditions is required to offset historic damage done in order to reach 100% individual sustainability on that variable. Historic damage was the “current damage” of the past. Both historically and today, higher income individuals spent and consumed more and thus created more “current damage”. To apply environmental restoration, the total of historic damage assigned is calculated on a per dollar spending basis, irrespective of the product or service purchased. The amount of restoration to be applied for each historic damage variable must be set such that the approximated original (pre-industrial) conditions for the underlying variable will be restored over the shortest possible period. Historic damage variables operate in a similar but opposite way to allowance variables; while for allowance variables a “usage allowance” exists, representing the maximum resource amount an individual can use sustainably, for historic variables a “historic damage” amount is assigned to products and services per dollar spending. To be 100% sustainable on this metric, the amount of environmental restoration applied must be equal to the amount of historic damage assigned to the product. Restoration of historic E-damage applies to damage and loss of wildlife areas, damage or loss to freshwater systems (water quality and amount), damage and loss of soils (amounts, structure, pollution and acidity) and (except for carbon sequestration) needs to be applied per ecoregion. Using carbon (C) sequestration as an example; the historic C-emissions assigned per dollar spending for a given year can be set to 0.60 kgCO₂/\$. A \$100 product would be assigned historic CO₂ emissions of $U_{CO_2,HD} = \$100 * 0.60 \text{ kgCO}_2/\$ = 60 \text{ kgCO}_2$. A reference individual would be assigned the same amount of CO₂ for \$100 spent and thus $U_{CO_2,HD,Ref} = 60 \text{ kgCO}_2$. This means that $u_{CO_2,HD} = U_{CO_2,HD} / U_{CO_2,HD,Ref} = 1.0$ under all circumstances as long as sufficient C-sequestration is available. To be 100% sustainable, these historic CO₂ emissions need to be fully sequestered at time of product purchase ($P_{CO_2,HD,Ref} = 60 \text{ kgCO}_2$). If the C-sequestration applied meets requirements ($P_{CO_2,HD} = 60 \text{ kg}$) then $p_{CO_2,HD} = P_{CO_2,HD} / P_{CO_2,HD,Ref} = 1.0$. If insufficient capacity is available and only 40% can be supplied, then $p_{CO_2,HD} = P_{CO_2,HD} / P_{CO_2,HD,Ref} = 24 / 60 = 0.4$.

In general for all historic damage variables under reference conditions, the amount of environmental restoration required is equal to the historic damage assigned to the product and in that case both amounts can be fully absorbed as IHDA: $p_{n,IHDA} = u_{m,IHDA}$. If less than the required amount of historic restoration is applied, then $p_{n,IHDA} < u_{m,IHDA}$ and the balance of historic damage is carried by the labor output. The IHDA is:

$$p_{n,IHDA} = u_{m,IHDA} = \text{MIN}(u_{m,HD,Ref}, p_{n,HD,Cons}) \quad (6)$$

where $p_{n,IHDA}$ = normalized individual sustainable historic damage absorption for conservation variable p_n , associated with historic damage variable u_m
 where $u_{m,IHDA}$ = normalized individual sustainable historic damage absorption for historic damage variable u_m
 where $u_{m,HD,Ref}$ = normalized reference amount of historic damage assigned to the consumption for the reference individual
 where $p_{n,HD,Cons}$ = normalized actual conservation applied for conservation variable p_n , associated with historic damage variable u_m

For historic damage, the required application of conservation will be delayed until sufficient means of conservation are available, while amounts assigned on a per dollar basis will be adjusted to availability.

4. Results and Discussion

For the IMAC system, the EH-impacts of the labor output of all ISCSs are inputs to Product Supply Chain Steps representing products and services (PSCS). In turn the outputs of PSCSs represent the EH-impacts of all products and services consumed by individuals (6, 7). Without removing amounts of resources that are used sustainably by each individual and without removing environmental damage done and conservation applied from the Individual Supply Chain Steps (ISCS) the addition of all environ-human (EH) impacts that enter the ISCS would lead to ever increasing and therefore meaningless EH-impacts of the labor output. The effective use of the ISCS therefore hinges on the ability to calculate the EH impact amounts that can and must be sustainably removed from the individual supply chain step as Individual Sustainable Absorption (ISA). The ability to correctly calculate the ISA and deduct these from ISCS inputs, creates an ISCS for which the labor output represents meaningful EH impact values. While the calculation of the ISA is different for each type of variable, the calculations are simple and can be carried out at large scales using the EH impacts that are inputs to the ISCS. The calculation of ISA allows the effective application and massive expansion of all types of environmental and human condition conservations. ISA allows a potentially fast return to pre-industrial environmental conditions (e.g. reversal of global warming and restoration of global biodiversity and elimination of water scarcity) and allows large improvements in human conditions. The most accurate EH impacts will be calculated for products and services using Product Supply Chain Step calculations (PSCS). As long as such PSCS outputs are not available, estimated values will be used. Estimation methods for EH impacts of products & services and for labor outputs will be presented in a separate article. Using these methods, the individual EH impacts of all individuals on Earth can be calculated. Comparing the actual impacts for each EH impact variable to the same EH impact variable under reference conditions, allows the calculation of individual sustainability for all variable types. Additional details concerning sustainability calculations will be presented in a separate article.

5. Methods

5.1. Use of Units

Labor Hours and Salary

Most goods and services have a price that is paid each time a transaction is made. Some payments can be expressed as monthly payments (apartment rent) but in those cases it may be treated as a separate payment for the use of the apartment for the next month. The ISCS figures and the associated EH-impact balance calculations represent a set period (a day, week or month). The words “salary” or “wage” is ambiguous, since they are both used to indicate the single payment amount (\$) and the amount paid per period (\$/period). To clarify this, the payment amount over time can be expressed as the “salary rate” (say \$ 400/week), while the payment itself “C” can be called the “salary paid”. The original variable “C” used in all ISCS [L, U, P] | [C] notations expresses the salary paid and the sum of all payments made for products and services consumed during the period and is expressed in \$, not in \$/period. Salary rate * period worked = 400 \$/w * 1 week = \$ 400 salary paid (C = \$ 400).

The same applies to hours worked. Working 40 versus 80 hours every week can be referred to as “labor intensities” expressed as 40 h/w versus 80 h/w, while over the defined period of one week the employee hours worked, were respectively 40 and 80 expressed in hours. As a human condition impact variable, the hours worked alone tell little and need to be expressed per unit time. Workers working in sweatshops half the year, while being unemployed the

other half of the year could still work ~ 40 h/w on average. A long period used can thus obscure the actual sweatshop conditions. Each ISCS figure or table represents a period, which must be specified in the figure or table or within the figure or table description. Once the period is specified, the labor hours worked are collected as hours. Used the collection period, the *labor intensity* can be calculated (h/d) and converted to other units where needed. The original variable “L” used to express the labor hours in all ISCS [L, U, P] | [C] notations is thus expressed in hours (h). To input values into data input sheets, the labor intensity of (say) 40 h/w can to be converted to the hours worked: $L = \text{Labor intensity (h/w)} * \text{period worked (w)} = 40 \text{ h/w} * 1 \text{ week} = 40 \text{ h}$.

Current Damage Variables

For C-emissions, each product to be sold must be assigned a C-emission amount, expressed in kg. Since amounts must be expressed in the same units to allow conversion free addition and subtraction in ISCS calculations, all C-emissions ISCS inputs and outputs must be expressed in the same units of mass (e.g. kg, ton). However, to calculate individual sustainability, the individual C-emission averages are compared to the national or global average individual emissions, both calculated over the same time period. Therefore, to calculate individual sustainability with respect to C-emissions, the units used are kg/period or ton/period. The likely most used options are: tonCO₂/year, tonCO₂/month, kgCO₂/week and kgCO₂/day.

Area Use Variables

For CA use, each product made and service provided must be assigned a CA amount used over a specified period, expressed in units reflecting “area * period”. For use of original variables, the likely most used options are Ha.y, m².y and m².d. Since amounts must be expressed in the same units to be added and subtracted easily in the ISCS calculations, all CA use ISCS inputs and outputs must be expressed in the same units like m².d or equivalent

Variable Type	Example Variable Used	Variable and Units for Product, Service or Labor	Variable and Units for Individual over Period of 1 Day	Variable and Units for Individual over Period of 1 Week
Current Damage	CO2 emissions	U (kg)	U per day (kg/d)	U per week (kg/w)
Historic Damage	CO2 emissions	U (kg)	U per day (kg/d)	U per week (kg/w)
Allowance	Cultivated Area Use	U (m ² .d)	U per day (m ²)	U per week (m ²)
Allowance	Labor Hours	L (h)	L per day (h/d)	L per week (h/w)
Allowance	Salary paid	S (\$)	S per day (\$/d)	S per week (\$/w)

Table 1a: Variables indicated by their customary letters and expressed in their units for selected periods, for current damage, historic damage and allowance variables as used in ISCS figures and associated tables and calculations. For environmental impacts the values are added over the period and expressed as units per period.

options. To calculate individual sustainability, individual CA use values are compared to national or global average individual CA use, both expressed over the same time period. Therefore, to calculate individual sustainability with respect to CA use, the units used are area*period/period. The likely most used options are: Ha.y/y (= Ha), m².y/y (= m²), m².month/month (= m²), m².w/w (= m²) and m².d/d (= m²).

The same units apply to other surface area related E-impacts like wildlife area conserved, watershed area used for collection of its precipitation, watershed area conserved for its water collection and inventory, coastal areas at risk of flooding and coastal areas protected from flooding by dike systems. Expressed as normalized variables, all variables are unit-less and independent of the periods used.

5.2. PSLA for Human Condition Variables

Variable U_m can represent different types of E-impacts each with different units. For example; U_m can represent CA use with units Ha.m or CO₂ emissions with units kg or soil loss with units kg or soil degradation with yet unknown units. The same diversity in units applies to the various conservation variables P_n . Within the ISCS notation [L, U, P] | [C], U and L represent human and environmental resource use, while P and C represent conservation applied to render the resource use sustainable (for P) and humane (for C). In analogy to variables U_m , variable L_x can reflect various H-impacts variables related to labor, while C_y can reflect various variables related to salary compensations, all with different units. Variables L, U, P and C are members of collection of elements $A^* = \{A, \dots, Z\}$, but each of variables L, U, P and C can be defined as collection of elements: $L = \{L_1, \dots, L_x\}$, $U = \{U_1, \dots, U_m\}$, $P = \{P_1, \dots, P_n\}$ and $C = \{C_1, \dots, C_y\}$.

Labor hours worked (L), wages paid (C) and the accounting periods over which these two H-impacts are accumulated are among the most important human condition variables. These three variables allow calculation of the labor hour intensity (LHI in h/d) and the salary rate (\$/d, \$/w, \$/m, \$/y). The hours worked L (h) and the salary paid (\$) are always carried as part of the EH impact variable notation [L, U, P] | [C]. However, sweatshop conditions identified for products in upstream ISCSs drop quickly to non-objectionable values when employees in downstream ISCSs work 40 h/w. In addition, “signals” for sweatshop conditions are less likely to show when employees work part-time. It would be more informative to look at the distribution of LHIs over all full-time working individuals that make a product or provided a service. This would need to be a one-sided distribution (the side reflecting higher than the reference LHIs), since it is not meaningful to include the part of the distribution representing part-time employees. Since the IMACS’ database contains all ISCS and PSCS records, the *mean* and *standard deviation* (SD) of the LHI for the last X layers of upstream ISCSs could be calculated. The percentage of individuals with a LHI larger than any value above LHI_{Ref} could be calculated. For $X = \infty$ all participating global employees would be included and all distributions would be the same. The number of upstream ISCSs layers X that should be included needs to be optimized to create the most discriminating and useful indicator for LHI.

The collection of elements $L = \{ L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4, \dots, L_z \}$, represents H-impacts, H-condition variables and calculated values,

where L_1 = the accounting period over which the labor hours are counted

where L_2 = the number of labor hours worked over the accounting period

where L_3 = the average of the LHI of individual consumption and the LHI of his/her own labor

where L_4 = the number of upstream ISCS layers included

where L_5 = the mean of the LHI over all ISCS layers that are included

where L_6 = the SD of the LHI over all ISCS layers that are included

Early after first implementation, only the three members of L would be used $L = \{ L_1, L_2, L_3 \}$. With the increasing availability of participating products, six members of L can be used: $L = \{ L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4, L_5, L_6 \}$. Once participation is sufficiently high to meaningfully include more ISCS layers, the value of L_4 can be gradually increased to the value with the highest level of discrimination for LHI. Collection of elements L can be extended to include more labor conditions related variables. Since labor hours worked is the main labor related impact variable L is represented by labor hours (L_2) in the notation [L, U, P] | [C], while the accounting period (L_1) must be indicated in the figure, in the description of the figure or table, or in the accompanying text.

A similar approach is followed for variable C (salary paid) or its normalized version c , already part of collection of elements $A = \{ a, \dots, z \}$. The best approach would be to define C itself as a collection of elements $C = \{ c_1, \dots, c_z \}$,

where c_1 = the accounting period over which the salary payments are counted

where c_2 = the amount of salary paid (\$)

where c_3 = the individual salary expressed as dollar per period (\$/w, \$/m, \$/y)

where c_4 = the number of ISCS layers included

where c_5 = the mean of individual salary rate over all ISCS layers that are included

where c_6 = the SD of the individual salary rate over all ISCS layers that are included

More members can be added reflecting other aspects of compensation (paid vacation and holidays, pension plan aspects, etc.). Very early after first implementation, only the first three members of C would be used $C = \{ c_1, c_2, c_3 \}$. At a later stage the first six members of C would be included; $C = \{ c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, c_6 \}$. Once participation is sufficiently high to meaningfully include more upstream ISCS layers, the value of c_4 can be gradually increased to the value with the highest level of discrimination for salary rate.

Similar but different to LHI, only salary rate distribution data (mean and SD) for the salary rates below the reference salary rates are here of interest, since we want to know which fraction of all salary rates are significantly below the reference salary rate. The reference salary rates reflect two values; the short term “hourly pay” (\$/h) and the longer term “living wage” (\$/y). Both differs per geographic location and needs to be carried as one of the members of the collection of elements C.

As outlined above, members of U, P, L and C can represent variable values for EH-impacts, EH-conditions or derived values. For EH-impacts an impact balance can be made over each ISCS. No impact balance can be made for EH-conditions variables that do not represent EH-impacts, but need to be collected to aid in calculation of derived values (i.e. accounting periods, the number of supply chain layers included, etc.). For such EH-conditions variables, no impact balances can be made and no PSA calculations apply.

5.3. ISRA Example for Environmental Allowance Variables

The reference value (allowance) for *Cultivated Area-use (CA)*, is set to 0.8 Ha. Over the period considered this corresponds to 0.8 Ha * 1 week = $U_{Ref} = 0.8$ Ha.w. Over a one week period, the employee worked 60 hours and earned \$ 800. All income is spent on goods and services as a single purchase. The \$ 800 purchase of products and services consumed reflects 44 h of labor and 4 Ha.w of cultivated area use. Initially no conservation is available. For the modified case the required conservation is applied as a 2nd purchase immediately following the primary purchase. All employee salary earned flows in resource direction and ends up flowing out with moneys paid for goods and services purchased. The average ratio R_{Bio} for the purchases made = 1.5. To simplify the example, all potential location based impacts (LBI) are combined with goods and services purchased. For this scenario we now have the following original variable values:

Labor hours worked:	$L_{Empl} = 60$ h, $L_{Consumption} = 44$ h and $L_{Ref} = 40$ h
Salary and consumption payments:	$C_{Sal} = 800$ \$, $C_{Consumption} = 800$ \$ and $C_{Ref} = 400$ \$
Cultivated area used:	$U_{Cons} = 4$ Ha.w and $U_{Ref} = 0.8$ Ha.w.
Reference wildlife area to be protected:	$P_{Ref} = U_{Ref} * R_{Bio} = 0.8$ Ha.w * 1.5 = 1.2 Ha.w
Total wildlife area (WA) to be protected:	$P_{Req} = U_{Cons} * R_{Bio} = 4$ Ha.w * 1.5 = 6 Ha.w
Wildlife area (WA) protected (base case):	$P_{Cons} = 0$ Ha.w

The original variable values can be presented in the ISCS notation [L, U, P] | [C] for the products and services consumed and the individual labor hours worked (rows 1 and 2 of [table 1b](#)). We can only calculate rows 3 and 4

+ Consumption + LBI input:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [44 , 4 , 0] [800] .
+ Own work hour input:	[L]	= [60]
- ISRA output:	[L, U, P]	= [40 , 0 , 0]
= Labor output:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [64 , 4 , 0] [800]

Table 1b: ISCS EH-impacts for Cultivated Area used, expressed as original variables under non-reference conditions.

after variable normalization. Normalization of the original variable values in [table 1b](#) (first two rows) gives:

Individual labor hours:	$l_{Empl} = L_{Empl} / L_{Ref} = 60$ h / 40 h = 1.5
Employee salary earned:	$c_{Sal} = C_{Sal} / C_{Ref} = \$ 800 / \$ 400 = 2 = c_{Cons}$
Labor hours of consumption:	$l_{Cons} = L_{Cons} / L_{Ref} = 44$ h / 40 h = 1.1
Resource use of consumption:	$u_{Cons} = U_{Cons} / U_{Ref} = 4$ Ha.w / 0.8 Ha.w = 5.0
Base case conservation applied:	$p_{Cons} = P_{Cons} / P_{Ref} = 0$ Ha.w / 1.2 Ha.w = 0
Modified case conservation applied:	$p_{Cons} = P_{Cons} / P_{Ref} = 6$ Ha.w / 1.2 Ha.w = 5

These normalized variable values are presented for the base case in ISCS notation in [table 2](#) (rows 1 and 2). The ISRA is calculated as:

$$l_{ISA} = \text{MIN}(1, l_{Empl}, l_{cons}) = \text{MIN}(1, 1.5, 1.1) = 1$$

$$u_{m,ISA} = p_{n,ISA} = \text{MIN}(1, u_{Cons}, p_{Cons}) = \text{MIN}(1, 5, 0) = 0$$

The normalized variable values for the ISRA are added to [table 2](#) (row 3) and the labor output is calculated (row 4) as the sum of ISCS inputs minus the ISRA output. The normalized variable values for the ISRA and labor outputs

+ Consumption input:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [1.1 , 5 , 0] [2]
+ Own work hour input:	[l]	= [1.5]
- ISRA output:	[l, u, p]	= [1 , 0 , 0]
= Labor output:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [1.6, 5 , 0] [2]

Table 2: Individual supply chain step inputs and outputs for base case expressed as normalized variable values.

are converted back to original variable values by multiplication with each corresponding reference value and added to [table 1b](#) (rows 3, 4). For the modified case the required conservation is purchased immediately following the

+ Consumption input:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [44 , 4 , 6] [800] .
+ Own work hour input:	[L]	= [60]
- ISRA output:	[L, U, P]	= [40 , 0.8 , 1.2]
= Labor output:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [64 , 3.2 , 4.8] [800]

Table 3: Individual supply chain step inputs and outputs for modified case expressed as original variable values.

primary purchase of goods and services. With the required wildlife area now protected in the name of the individual, the individual conservation applied is: $p_{Cons} = P_{Cons} / P_{Ref} = 6 \text{ Ha.w} / 1.2 \text{ Ha.w} = 5$. (See first rows 1 and 2 of [table 4.](#)) For the modified case, the ISRA results for $u_{m,ISRA}$ and $p_{n,ISRA}$ are recalculated:

$$u_{m,ISRA} = p_{n,ISRA} = \text{MIN}(1, u_{Cons}, p_{Cons}) = \text{MIN}(1, 5, 1) = 1$$

The normalized variable values for the ISRA are added to [table 4](#) (row 3) and the labor output is calculated (row 4) as the sum of ISCS inputs minus the ISRA output. The normalized variable values for the ISRA and labor outputs

+ Consumption input:	$[l, u, p] [c] = [1.1, 5, 5] [2]$
+ Own work hour input:	$[l] [c] = [1.5] [1]$
- ISRA output:	$[l, u, p] [c] = [1, 1, 1] [1]$
= Labor output:	$[l, u, p] [c] = [1.6, 4, 4] [2]$

Table 4: Individual supply chain step inputs and outputs for modified case expressed as normalized variable values.

are converted back to original variable values by multiplication with each corresponding reference value and added to [table 3](#) (rows 3 and 4). Under reference normal conditions, the labor output corresponds to $[l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 0, 0] | [1]$. The value $u_{Lab,Ref} = 0$, reflects the CA use of one world under reference conditions corresponding to a CA use sustainability $S_{CA} = 1 / (1 + u_{Lab}) = 1 / (1 + 0) = 100\%$. For the modified case, the CA use sustainability of the labor output corresponds to $S_{CA} = 1 / (1 + u_{Lab}) = 1 / (1 + 4) = 20\%$. For the base case, the CA use sustainability of the labor corresponds to $S_{CA} = 1 / (1 + u_{Lab}) = 1 / (1 + 5) = 17\%$. For the modified and base cases the CA use corresponds to respectively the use of five and six worlds. The biodiversity or wildlife area (WA) sustainability is calculated as $S_{WA} = p / p_{Req}$. Under reference conditions $p_{Req} = p_{Ref} = 1$. $S_{WA,Ref} = p / p_{Req} = 1 / 1 = 100\%$. For the modified case $S_{WA} = p / p_{Req} = 5 / 5 = 100\%$, while for the base case $S_{WA} = p / p_{Req} = 0 / 5 = 0\%$.

[Table 4](#) shows that overtime worked immediately increases the labor hours of the labor product and consequently of the products and services sold. The value for $L_{Lab} = 64 \text{ h}$ over a week corresponds to a labor intensity of 64 h/w . The formula used to calculate the labor hours removed from the supply chain as ISA uses $l_{ISA} = \text{MIN}(l_{Ref}, l_{Empl}, l_{cons})$. With $l_{Ref} = 1$, the values calculated for l_{ISA} that are never larger than unity. This means that any access labor hours collected would never be reduced. While this was done intentionally in order to catch inhumane labor conditions (sweatshops) it was not intended to cause an issue for slightly higher than reference hours worked. One way to solve this issue is to use a value for l_{Ref} slightly higher than unity under conditions of slightly elevated labor intensities. For example, for conditions where $l_{cons} > 1$ and $1 \leq l_{Empl} < 1.5$ the value for l_{Ref} could be increased to $l_{Ref} = 1.1$. This would allow a gradual reduction of the labor intensity for modest overtime worked, but still accumulate labor hours worked for supply chain sections far exceeding reference conditions.

5.4. ICDA Example for Current Damage Variables

Current carbon emissions are used as an example of current damage. CO₂ emissions vary strongly per dollar spent on single products, but this variation becomes smaller with increasing sizes of the baskets of goods and services consumed. For simplicity of the example, I assume that CO₂ emissions are on average 0.70 kgCO₂/\$. The average (representative) individual works 36 per week (h/w), earns \$ 1,000 per month (\$/m) and has the average CO₂ emissions per dollar spending, leading to emissions of 0.7 tCO₂/m, reflecting the representative emissions. The reference individual works 36 h/w, earns \$ 1,000/m and (per definition) has no CO₂ emissions. For an individual working 18 h/w, earning \$ 3,000/m and a total consumption reflecting average labor intensity and the average CO₂-emissions per dollar spending, the emissions are 2.1 tCO₂/m. The accounting period used is one month. The required C-sequestration is equal to the amount emitted. For this accounting period, a \$ 3,000 salary is paid, 78 hours are worked and CO₂ emissions from total consumptions are ($\$ 3000 * 0.70 \text{ kgCO}_2/\$ =$) 2.1 tCO₂.

Accounting period:	One month
Labor hours:	$L_{Empl} = 78 \text{ h}$, $L_{Consumption} = 468 \text{ h}$ and $L_{Ref} = 156 \text{ h}$
Labor hour intensity:	$I_{Empl} = 18 \text{ h/w} = 78 \text{ l/m}$, $I_{Consumption} = 36 \text{ h/w} = 156 \text{ h/m}$
Salary and consumption payments:	$C_{Sal} = \$ 3,000$, $C_{Consumption} = \$ 3,000$ and $C_{Ref} = \$ 1,000$
CO ₂ emissions:	$U_{Cons} = 2.1 \text{ tCO}_2$, $U_{Repr} = 0.7 \text{ tCO}_2$ and $U_{Ref} = 0 \text{ tCO}_2$
CO ₂ sequestration required and representative:	$P_{Req} = 2.1 \text{ tCO}_2$, $P_{Repr} = 0.7 \text{ tCO}_2$

CO₂ sequestration purchased:

$$P_{\text{Cons}} = 0 \text{ tCO}_2 \text{ (base case), } P_{\text{Cons}} = 2.1 \text{ tCO}_2 \text{ (modified case),}$$

The original variable values can be presented in ISCS notation [L, U, P] | [C] for the products and services consumed and the individual labor hours worked (rows 1 and 2 of table 5). Rows 3 and 4 can only be calculated

+ Consumption + LBI input:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [468, 2.1, 0] [3000].
+ Own work hour input:	[L]	= [78]
- ICDA output:	[L, U, P]	= [78, 0, 0]
= Labor output:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [468, 2.1, 0] [3000]

Table 5: Individual supply chain step EH-impacts for current carbon dioxide emissions, expressed as original variable values under base case conditions over a period of one month. Units: L in h, U in tCO₂, P in tCO₂, C in \$.

after variable normalization. Normalization of the original variable values in table 1b (first two rows) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Individual labor hours:} & \quad l_{\text{Empl}} = L_{\text{Empl}} / L_{\text{Ref}} = 78 \text{ h} / 156 \text{ h} = 0.5 \\ \text{Labor hours of consumption:} & \quad l_{\text{Cons}} = L_{\text{Cons}} / L_{\text{Ref}} = 468 \text{ h} / 156 \text{ h} = 3.0 \\ \text{Employee salary earned:} & \quad c_{\text{Sal}} = C_{\text{Sal}} / C_{\text{Ref}} = \$ 3000 / \$ 1000 = 3 = c_{\text{Cons}} \\ \text{CO}_2 \text{ emissions of consumption:} & \quad u_{\text{Cons}} = U_{\text{Cons}} / U_{\text{Repr}} = 2.1 \text{ tCO}_2 / 0.7 \text{ tCO}_2 = 3.0 \\ \text{Base case conservation applied:} & \quad p_{\text{Cons}} = P_{\text{Cons}} / P_{\text{Repr}} = 0 \text{ tCO}_2 / 0.7 \text{ tCO}_2 = 0 \\ \text{Modified case conservation applied:} & \quad p_{\text{Cons}} = P_{\text{Cons}} / P_{\text{Repr}} = 2.1 \text{ tCO}_2 / 0.7 \text{ tCO}_2 = 3.0 \end{aligned}$$

These normalized variable values are presented for the base case in ISCS notation in table 6 (rows 1 and 2).

The ICDA is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} l_{\text{ISA}} &= \text{MIN}(1, l_{\text{Empl}}, l_{\text{cons}}) = \text{MIN}(1, 0.5, 3) = 0.5 \\ u_{m, \text{ICDA}} = p_{n, \text{ICDA}} &= \text{MIN}(u_{m, \text{CD, Cons}}, p_{n, \text{CD, Cons}}) = \text{MIN}(3, 0) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The normalized variable values for the ICDA are added to table 6 (row 3) and the labor output is calculated (row 4) as the sum of ISCS inputs minus the ICDA output. The normalized variable values for the ICDA and labor outputs

+ Consumption input:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [3, 3, 0] [3]
+ Own work hour input:	[l]	= [0.5]
- ICDA output:	[l, u, p]	= [0.5, 0, 0]
= Labor output:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [3, 3, 0] [3]

Table 6: ISCS for normalized EH-impacts for current carbon dioxide emissions. Base case for a period of one month.

are converted back to original variable values by multiplication with each corresponding reference value and added to table 5 (rows 3 and 4). For the modified case the required conservation is purchased immediately following the

+ Consumption input:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [468, 2.1, 2.1] [3000].
+ Own work hour input:	[L]	= [78]
- ICDA output:	[L, U, P]	= [78, 2.1, 2.1]
= Labor output:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [468, 0, 0] [3000]

Table 7: Individual supply chain step EH-impacts for current carbon dioxide emissions, expressed as original variable values under modified conditions over a period of one month. Units: L in h, U in tCO₂, P in tCO₂, C in \$.

primary purchase of goods and services (table 7). With the required amount of CO₂ now sequestered in the name of the individual, the normalized individual conservation applied is: $p_{\text{Cons}} = P_{\text{Cons}} / P_{\text{Ref}} = 2.1 \text{ tCO}_2 / 0.7 \text{ tCO}_2 = 3$. (table 8 rows 1 and 2). The ICDA results for $u_{m, \text{ICDA}}$ and $p_{n, \text{ICDA}}$ are recalculated:

$$u_{m, \text{ICDA}} = p_{n, \text{ICDA}} = \text{MIN}(u_{m, \text{CD, Cons}}, p_{n, \text{CD, Cons}}) = \text{MIN}(3, 3) = 3$$

The normalized variable values for the ICDA are added to table 8 (row 3) and the labor output is calculated (row 4) as the sum of ISCS inputs minus the ICDA output. The normalized variable values for the ICDA and labor outputs

+ Consumption input:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [3, 3, 3] [3]
+ Own work hour input:	[l]	= [0.5]
- ICDA output:	[l, u, p]	= [0.5, 3, 3]
= Labor output:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [3, 0, 0] [3]

Table 8: ISCS for normalized EH-impacts for current carbon dioxide emissions. Modified case for a period of one month.

are converted back to original variable values by multiplication with each corresponding reference value and added to [table 7](#) (rows 3 and 4).

5.5. IHDA Example for Historic Damage Variables

Historic carbon emissions are used as an example of historic damage. The C-sequestration offsetting historic emissions will grow with the installed C-sequestration capacity and will vary over the ~ 40-year period targeted for return to pre-industrial conditions. For the example date, the historic emissions assigned to each end-user transaction are set to 0.80 kgCO₂/\$. The reference individual works 36 h/w, earns \$ 1,000/m and has reference CO₂ emissions of 0.8 tCO₂/m. The average individual works 36 per week (h/w), earns \$ 1,000 per month (\$/m) and has the same CO₂ emissions of 0.8 tCO₂/m. For an individual earning \$ 3,000/m, a one-month accounting period and assigned historic CO₂-emissions of 0.80 kgCO₂/\$, the required C-sequestration is equal to the amount emitted: P_{Req} = U = 2.4 tCO₂/m.

Accounting period:	One month
Labor hours:	L _{Empl} = 78 h, L _{Consumption} = 468 h and L _{Ref} = 156 h
Labor hour intensity:	I _{Empl} = 18 h/w = 78 l/m, I _{Consumption} = 36 h/w = 156 h/m
Salary and consumption payments:	C _{Sal} = \$ 3,000, C _{Consumption} = \$ 3,000 and C _{Ref} = \$ 1,000
CO ₂ emissions:	U _{Cons} = 2.4 tCO ₂ , and U _{Ref} = 0.8 tCO ₂
CO ₂ sequestration required and representative:	P = 2.4 tCO ₂ , P _{Ref} = 0.8 tCO ₂
CO ₂ sequestration purchased:	P _{Cons} = 0 tCO ₂ (base case), P _{Cons} = 2.4 tCO ₂ (modified case),

The original variable values can be presented in ISCS notation [L, U, P] | [C] for the products and services consumed and the individual labor hours worked (rows 1 and 2 of [table 9](#)). We can only calculate rows 3 and 4

+ Consumption + LBI input:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [468, 2.4, 0] [3000]
+ Own work hour input:	[L]	= [78]
- IHDA output:	[L, U, P]	= [78, 0, 0]
= Labor output:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [468, 2.4, 0] [3000]

Table 9: ISCS EH-impacts for historic CO₂ emissions, expressed as original variables. Base case over a period of one month. Units: L in h, U in tCO₂, P in tCO₂, C in \$.

after variable normalization. Normalization of the original variable values in [table 1b](#) (first two rows) gives:

Individual labor hours:	$l_{Empl} = L_{Empl} / L_{Ref} = 78 \text{ h} / 156 \text{ h} = 0.5$
Labor hours of consumption:	$l_{Cons} = L_{Cons} / L_{Ref} = 468 \text{ h} / 156 \text{ h} = 3.0$
Employee salary earned:	$c_{Sal} = C_{Sal} / C_{Ref} = \$ 3000 / \$ 1000 = 3 = c_{Cons}$
CO ₂ emissions of consumption:	$u_{Cons} = U_{Cons} / U_{Ref} = 2.4 \text{ tCO}_2 / 0.8 \text{ tCO}_2 = 3.0$
Base case conservation applied:	$p_{Cons} = P_{Cons} / P_{Ref} = 0 \text{ tCO}_2 / 0.8 \text{ tCO}_2 = 0$
Modified case conservation applied:	$p_{Cons} = P_{Cons} / P_{Ref} = 2.4 \text{ tCO}_2 / 0.8 \text{ tCO}_2 = 3.0$

These normalized variable values are presented for the base case in ISCS notation in [table 6](#) (rows 1 and 2).

The IHDA is calculated as:

$$l_{ISA} = \text{MIN}(1, l_{Empl}, l_{cons}) = \text{MIN}(1, 0.5, 3) = 0.5$$

$$u_{m,IHDA} = p_{n,IHDA} = \text{MIN}(u_{m,HD,Ref}, p_{n,HD,Cons}) = \text{MIN}(3, 0) = 0$$

The normalized variable values for the IHDA are added to [table 10](#) (row 3) and the labor output is calculated (row 4) as the sum of ISCS inputs minus the IHDA output. The normalized variable values for the IHDA and labor outputs

+ Consumption input:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [3, 3, 0] [3]
+ Own work hour input:	[l]	= [0.5]
- IHDA output:	[l, u, p]	= [0.5, 0, 0]
= Labor output:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [3, 3, 0] [3]

Table 10: ISCS inputs and outputs for historic CO₂ emissions; base case expressed as normalized variable values.

are converted back to original variable values by multiplication with each corresponding reference value and added to [table 11](#) (rows 3 and 4). For the modified case the required conservation is purchased immediately following the

+ Consumption input:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [468 , 2.4 , 2.4] [3000] .
+ Own work hour input:	[L]	= [78]
- IHDA output:	[L, U, P]	= [78 , 2.4 , 2.4]
= Labor output:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [468 , 0 , 0] [3000]

Table 11: ISCS EH-impacts for historic CO₂ emissions, expressed as original variables. Modified case over a period of one month. Units: L in h, U in tCO₂, P in tCO₂, C in \$.

primary purchase of goods and services (table 11). With the required amount of CO₂ now sequestered in the name of the individual, the normalized individual conservation applied is: $p_{Cons} = P_{Cons} / P_{Ref} = 2.4 \text{ tCO}_2 / 0.8 \text{ tCO}_2 = 3$. (Table 12 rows 1 and 2). The IHDA results for $u_{m,IHDA}$ and $p_{n,IHDA}$ are recalculated:

$$u_{m,IHDA} = p_{n,IHDA} = \text{MIN}(u_{m,HD,Ref}, p_{n,HD,Cons}) = \text{MIN}(3, 3) = 3$$

The normalized variable values for the IHDA are added to table 8 (row 3) and the labor output is calculated (row 4) as the sum of ISCS inputs minus the IHDA output. The normalized variable values for the IHDA and labor outputs

+ Consumption input:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [3 , 3 , 3] [3]
+ Own work hour input:	[l]	= [0.5]
- IHDA output:	[l, u, p]	= [0.5 , 3 , 3]
= Labor output:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [3 , 0 , 0] [3]

Table 12: Individual supply chain step inputs and outputs for modified case expressed as normalized variable values.

are converted back to original variable values by multiplication with each corresponding reference value and added to table 11 (rows 3 and 4).

6. References

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